

PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE OFFICERS

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Abstract. *This article presents thoughts and opinions about scientific and pedagogical formation of professional competence of future officers, professional competence allows future officers to fully express themselves in any conditions.*

Keywords: *Competence, competency, informational competence, creativeness, communicative, extreme.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the system of training military specialists for all military units, institutions and organizations belonging to the Ministry of Defense is being improved in accordance with the requirements of the time. In addition, the existing training programs are being reworked, in which it is required that personnel pay more attention to the practice of learning weapons and combat techniques. One of the urgent problems is to provide all available opportunities for our people to lead a peaceful life and, most importantly, to ensure the strength of our integrity achieved as a result of independence. On the basis of the military reforms carried out by our country, all kinds of activities aimed at ensuring stability in our country are aimed at forming the personality of the future officer.

With these considerations in mind, in order to anticipate and eliminate threats to the stability of the state, future officers must understand their negative nature, be correct, clear and firm, regardless of the situation. It is necessary to be a competent person who can make decisions and is faithful to his duty and oath before the Motherland.

Therefore, military personnel (officers, sergeants, private soldiers) are required to constantly improve their skills in terms of combat readiness physically, mentally, immediately and professionally. This, in turn, is a sign that it is important for every serviceman, especially officers and sergeants, to understand and understand the essence of professional competence in the Armed Forces of our country.

➤ LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The essence of this issue is that in order for the cadets studying at the Higher Military Educational Institutions to become soldiers with intellectual potential, excellent knowledge, independent thinking and intellectual abilities, the pedagogue who educates them teachers, officers and sergeants must have social, personal, professional, extreme, psychological and other characteristics of competence.

The formation of professional competence of future officers means, first of all, the formation of educated and intellectual potential, strong will and strong training in fulfilling the duty of a military man, love for family, homeland and, of course, profession.

Competence is taken from the English language, the dictionary meaning of "competence" is "ability". Content refers to the concepts of "successful use of theoretically acquired knowledge in professional activity, high-level professional qualification, skill".

Competency is a constantly developing classification of a person during his professional activity, which is the ability to learn and solve problems that arise in any situation, to make firm decisions, the knowledge, skills and experience acquired and learned in the course of education. is the ability to apply skills and life experiences to professional activities.

The above-mentioned concepts of competence and competence have a broader meaning than the concepts of knowledge, skill, and competence, and they describe the qualities of a person such as worldview, ability to think, ability to make quick decisions, character and intelligence. contains z.

Currently, a number of studies are being carried out on the definition of the concept of competence and its important components and their content, as well as on the problems of their formation and development in various spheres of activity, including the Defense system.

Here are some qualities of professional competence:

- Social competence
- Personal competence
- Technological competence
- Special (or professional competence)
- Extreme competence
- Psychological, methodological, etc.

1. Social competence - to be active in social relations, to have skills, competences and ways of communication and rules of conduct in professional activities;

2. Special competence is the ability to prepare for the organization of activities at an independent level, to rationally solve the assigned tasks, to evaluate the results of one's activities, to independently acquire new knowledge and skills in one's specialty. On the basis of special competence, the following competences are highlighted:

- methodical competence - organizing the pedagogical process using various modern methods, choosing the right forms of activity and being able to use the selected methods effectively;

- information competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary and useful information and using it appropriately and effectively in activities;

- **creative competence** - critical and creative approach to professional activity, ability to demonstrate one's creativity;

- **innovative competence** - promotion of new ideas to increase the quality of education and develop the efficiency of the educational process, their effective application in practical processes;

- **communicative competence** - being able to communicate sincerely with the participants of the educational process, that is, cadets, fully hear their opinions and have a positive influence on them.

3. Personal competence - to improve professional skills and qualifications in professional activities, to be able to fully demonstrate one's internal capabilities;

4. Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich BKM in professional activity, being able to use modern (multimedia, electronic board, computer) technologies.

5. Extreme competence - the ability to make a rational and firm decision in emergency situations (combat panic, suddenly receiving completely new orders).

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In addition to improving the quality of educational processes in higher military educational institutions, one of the main tasks of professors, officers and sergeants is to create conditions for the development and formation of the competence of cadets.

From a pedagogical point of view, the educational process of future officers is a part of teaching by educators (teacher, officer, sergeant, instructor) and learning by students. purposeful, systematic and cooperative activities.

In this process, the main pedagogical task of the teacher is as follows:

- organizing and leading the training activities of cadets;
- systematic and scientific description of the teaching material;
- creating interest and positive motivation in cadets for learning;
- formation of features of independent learning, development of skills and qualifications in cadets;
- development of military-professional skills;
- assessment of knowledge, skills and qualifications of cadets, as well as professional skills.

As a result of such activities, cadets will acquire relevant knowledge, skills and abilities, and at the same time, their thinking, feelings will develop, their will and character will be strengthened, and their mental readiness will be formed to act in the process of performing combat missions.

This, in turn, implies the rules for the effective use of wide experiences, the continuous development of professional, theoretical and practical knowledge acquired in accordance with the requirements of the time, and the formation of professional competence. Professional competence creates the basis for acquiring life experience skills in the process of organizing their professional activities.

In the course of their professional activities, senior officers should have the following skills:

- to improve professional, theoretical and practical knowledge, to constantly expand one's independent thinking ability, worldview, knowledge and experience, to obtain new information using information and communication technologies, to learn best practices;
- To conscientiously approach the fulfillment of the duty to the country and to serve sincerely, to preserve our material and spiritual wealth, to have a respectful relationship with our national values;
- formation of logical thinking skills, development of intelligence, observation, and intellectual potential related to knowledge, making non-standard decisions independently in stressful situations;
- perform military duties and responsibilities within the framework of general military regulations during the service period, behave decently in public places, pay attention to personal behavior, do not violate the regulations of the regulations;
- must have the ability to learn foreign languages, listen to audio and video texts, understand their meaning and analyze them, and communicate.

CONCLUSION

From the comments presented in the article, it can be concluded that in the formation of professional competence in officers, it is necessary to make changes in the content and form of the educational process in higher military educational institutions, that is, to train cadets not only for certain periods, but for the whole education. it is necessary to ensure activities based on them during the learning process. In addition to this, the theory of attitude is also important in the further development of professional competence of future officers, because attitude embodies the inclinations of a person and creates an opportunity to determine the professional orientation of a person.

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